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CONSUMER ELECTRONICS SOCIAL MEDIA MARKETING: FUTURE DIRECTIONS OF STUDY AND A SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the scholarly literature on social media marketing (SMM) in consumer electronics (CEs) for insight into the current state of the art, significant research issues covered, and implications for managerial and practice. Social media has enhanced the connection and interaction among businesses and clients in various industries, particularly the CEs industry. In order to accumulate and synthesise CEs-related research, a systematic literature review of scholarly studies on SMM was implemented. All CEs-SMM-related research was found and analysed using a review methodology that included automatic and manual searches in the EBSCO Host, Scopus, and Web of Science databases, with emerging important research themes divided into three categories. This study is valuable to academics and practitioners because it provides the first thorough and critical systematic review of scholarly research on SMM in CEs.

KEYWORDS: Systematic Review, Social Media Marketing, Consumer Electronics Brand, Consumer Behaviour, Consumer Electronics Industry.

1. INTRODUCTION

In modern society, people are surrounded by the Internet. People generate new information daily via the World Wide Web and social media connections. This information develops via relationships; everyone in a community is a catalyst in this dynamic process (Castro, 2022). Social media encourages the establishment of ties between users from different cultures, leading to a robust social structure (Kapoor *et al.*, 2018). People increasingly spend significant time on online communities, exchanging and exploring information continually. They utilise social media platforms for anything, including breaking news and information on major happenings, recreation, engaging with close companions, feedback and suggestions on services, goods, and places, treating psychological requirements, and managing their jobs (Kapoor *et al.*, 2018). Hence, social media is widely recognised as a mechanism that contributes to businesses' marketing objectives and approaches, especially in the area of consumer involvement, managing relationships, and interaction (Filo *et al.*, 2015; Saxena & Khanna, 2013).

Firms develop and offer online products via social networking sites to establish and sustain connections with clients and increase value for stakeholders through promoting communication, sharing knowledge, providing purchase suggestions, and generating customer reputation for existing goods or services (Yadav & Rahman, 2017b). Additionally, social media helps create, develop, and keep long-term customer connections, build brand awareness, influence consumer attitudes and behaviour, obtain comments, improve present offerings, and boost profits (Dwivedi *et al.*, 2021). Most businesses have incorporated social media links to facilitate communication and strengthen client relationships (Choi *et al.*, 2016; Yadav & Rahman, 2016).

The vast majority of extremely loyal customers is a sign of the uniqueness of CEs during the era of widespread mobile Internet usage. The use of social media facilitates the exchange and dissemination of knowledge amongst users, which improves their comprehension, perception, and brand credibility (Fu & Lai, 2016). Especially in emerging markets, consumers actively search for data through online media platforms and trust that they can get reliable and professional advice on multiple social media channels, such as brand communities and brand networks for CEs (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2019). Accordingly, for the CEs industry, SMM significantly impacts a company's reputation and reaction from clients (Sharma *et al.*, 2022).

Nonetheless, academic investigations on SMM in

CEs corporations are currently less focused and remain largely unexplored; there is a lack of research specifically targeting the CEs business (Pre *et al.*, 2022). The exploration of the promotional value of SMM in CEs businesses through a systematic evaluation and synthesis of existing studies has not been conducted yet. The limited investigations that have been done on this subject have frequently concentrated on a single usage of social media platforms for online retailers (Pre *et al.*, 2022), opinion leaders and opinion seekers (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2019), on brand equity and consumer response (Sharma *et al.*, 2022) or content marketing strategy (Fu & Lai, 2016). Thus, there is a study gap about the most recent developments in the field of SMM studies targeted at CEs brands.

This research seeks to address an empty spot in the available literature by conducting a systematic review of SMM studies in CEs brands in order to highlight major research themes and recommend future research directions. The purpose of this study is to provide a thorough comprehension or review of SMM in CEs businesses, as well as to identify research concerns that have already been addressed for researchers interested in conducting fresh investigations on this topic.

This study is structured as follows: The second part offers context for SMM and the development of CEs brands in modern times; the third part defines the method of study employed in completing this review, including data extraction and synthesis; the fourth part analyses results and findings and discusses the most significant topics of the study, as well as the theoretical and managerial effects for managerial study. The fifth part finishes by considering potential future study topics.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

2.1. *Development of Social Media Marketing*

Social media is defined as a collection of Web 2.0-based online and mobile sites with the capacity to interact and engage large numbers of people. These platforms enable users to distribute and geotag content created by users (text, images, video, audio, and games) at the micro, meso, and macro levels, as well as to work together and create communities (Ouiridi *et al.*, 2014). It can also be defined as "new media technologies facilitating interactivity and co-creation that enable the development and sharing of user-generated content among and between organisations (such as teams, government agencies, and media groups) and individuals (such as customers, athletes, and journalists)" (Filo *et al.*, 2015). Over the past few years, Scholars and experts

have scrutinised and explored several aspects of social media (Kapoor et al., 2018). It has been noted that social media applications are one of the most effective and pervasive influences on the majority of facets of people's lives (Alalwan et al., 2017).

Typically, when social media is mentioned, applications such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, YouTube, and Instagram come to mind. These applications are driven by user-generated content and are highly influential in a variety of fields, including purchasing/selling behaviour, entrepreneurship, political issues, and venture capital (Greenwood & Gopal, 2015). Inevitably, social media is widely recognised as a mechanism that contributes to businesses' marketing objectives and strategies, particularly in terms of customer engagement, customer relationship management, and communication (Filo et al., 2015; Saxena & Khanna, 2013).

Social media marketing (SMM) is the process that enables individuals to promote their products or services via online social networks and get access to a bigger community (Yong & Hassan, 2019). SMM may also be described as the efforts made by businesses to attract the attention of potential customers through the use of various Internet social media platforms (Magasic, 2016). In other words, SMM is the utilisation of social media technology, platforms, and software to produce, communicate, deliver, and trade products or services of value for an organisation's stakeholders (Tuten & Solomon, 2017). Companies create, communicate, and deliver online marketing products through social media platforms in order to build and maintain customer relationships and increase stakeholder value by enabling communication, sharing information, providing personalised purchase recommendations, and generating customer word-of-mouth about current and new products and services (Yadav & Rahman, 2017a).

SMM is the only kind of marketing that can reach and influence buyers at every stage of the purchasing process, from brand and product consideration to post-purchase decision making (Saravanakumar & Sugantha-Lakshmi, 2012). Customers on social media platforms can reach out to companies to get the latest news about their products or services. Different efforts in liking, commenting, and sharing increase customer engagement with the online brand community through social media (Pancer et al., 2019). Customers are likely to share positive purchasing experiences, and this online word of mouth (WOM) is highly influential: more than 85% of respondents said they had made a purchase based

on a blog recommendation, while 60% said they had made a purchase based on a Facebook recommendation (Clark & Melancon, 2013). Companies can build close relationships with consumers, understand their values, and maintain and increase brand awareness (Tarik & Adnan, 2018).

SMM can also customise information for customer groups, thus increasing customer loyalty (Buzzeto-More, 2013; Clark & Melancon, 2013). For clients seeking information, the advantage of social media is that it provides more available data, many types of user-file relationships, and many user-to-user interactions (Agichtein et al., 2008). Social media offers marketers the ability to target audiences and consumers based on the personal interests of site users. With this kind of targeted marketing and advertising, marketers can effectively reach potential customers (Nadaraja & Yazdanifard, 2013). SMM is more targeted at the target audience and may be an effective early indicator of what products will be popular (Stephen & Galak, 2012). It assists customers by providing customised information (Ibrahim, 2022). Social media marketing also makes it easier for companies to measure the effectiveness of advertisements to the company, and it also makes it possible for companies to target their advertisements to the consumers they need (Todor, 2016; Das & Lall, 2016).

Compared with traditional marketing campaigns, SMM has a significantly longer continuation effect, a higher action rate, and more response flexibility (Buzzeto-More, 2013). As a positive communication mode, SMM activities provide more possible communication relationships between customers and enterprises. This two-way relationship provides a wide range of information about the brand that is easily accessible to users or customers. SMM activities provide good opportunities for marketers to have a broader reach and build effective long-term relationships with consumers (Gautam & Sharma, 2017).

Moreover, communities for brands on social media strengthen consumer ties with the brand, increasing brand trust (Laroche et al., 2013). Online users can show empathy for a brand even if they cannot purchase the goods offered by a company, making social media management a significant tool for influencing relationship outcomes (Clark & Melancon, 2013). SMM initiatives can increase a brand's inner and social self-expression, which in turn can increase consumers' brand loyalty (Algharabat, 2017). In particular, because customers value consistent communication from the brand, it might increase their brand loyalty (Merisavo &

Raulas, 2004).

2.2. Social Media Marketing and Consumer Electronics

Consumer electronics brands are selected as the research category in this study. Consumer electronics (CE) are electronic equipment intended for purchase and usage by end users or consumers for non-commercial or professional reasons (Techopedia, 2014). With all the latest technologies available in consumer electronics, it can be difficult for consumers to choose the right product for their needs (Heitmann et al., 2007). There are also many consumer electronics brands, which adds to the difficulty of choice for consumers, leading them to rely on customised recommendations from social media (Trivedi & Sama, 2020). Because of the characteristics of search products, customers tend to rely on online reviews when acquiring consumer electronics brands, and these commodities are thus deemed to be appropriate for assessing consumers' informational behaviour (Jung & Kim, 2012). According to this, the consumption patterns and consumption decisions of consumer electronics consumers are largely affected by various information about brands on the Internet.

The development of social media has changed the way consumers of consumer electronics interact with or acquire information. The positive e-word of mouth generated by users on social networking sites and Facebook significantly affects brand attitudes and purchase intentions of consumer electronics products (Kudeshia & Kumar, 2017). Perceived ease of use, social media advertising, and e-word of mouth all directly impact the overall performance of online retail businesses in the consumer electronics industry (Pre et al., 2022). Additionally, in the consumer electronics industry, mentions in tweets on social media platforms (e.g., Twitter) to increase follower engagement have become important, such as Samsung's alliance with the prominent Korean group BTS through advertising to be part of its products or to be the face of the brand (Garcia-Rivera et al., 2022). When planning marketing communications for consumer electronics, there are obvious advantages

to choosing expert influencers (Trivedi & Sama, 2020).

However, the relevant academic literature on consumer electronics brands and social media marketing remains underdeveloped and fragmented, and the relationship that exists between social media and consumer electronics remains largely unexplored. Therefore, this study aims to illustrate the latest level of research on social media marketing for consumer electronics brands. It also provides clear propositions and future research directions, summarises the current state of research in the field and draws attention to potential future research opportunities.

3. METHODOLOGY

A systematic review is an approach that identifies existing research, selects and assesses contributions, analyses and synthesises data, and reports on the evidence in such a way that relatively unambiguous conclusions about what is known and what is unknown may be formed (Denyer & Tranfield, 2006). If this research base is inter-disciplinary and fast growing, like in social media marketing, the value of an SLR is increased (Rowley & Keegan, 2020).

3.1. Formulating Research Questions

The first step is to define the study's goal and scope (Rowley & Keegan, 2020). This study employed a systematic literature review approach to assess social media marketing academic literature focused on consumer electronics in order to help theory building and identify research areas that require additional examination.

Accordingly, the research question of this study was the following:

RQ1: What is the current state of the art and the main research questions relating to consumer electronics that have been addressed in the academic literature on social media marketing?

RQ2: What are the limitations and gaps in the current research of social media marketing in consumer electronics?

Fig. 1: Methodology Diagram.

3.2. Selecting Appropriate Databases

The second step is to concentrate on selecting acceptable databases for the search (Rowley & Keegan, 2020). According to Webster and Watson (2002), the search procedure should not be limited to a specific range of academic journals.

Thus, EBSCO Host, Scopus and Web of Science were selected as the vehicles for the literature search process. EBSCO Host was chosen as the database because it searches papers in multiple databases at the same time, including Emerald, Sage, Blackwell, and Science Direct, indicating its reach and capability for a systematic review (Bhimani et al., 2019).

In addition, Scopus is the largest peer-reviewed abstracts and citations database. Because research on social media marketing spans the globe and crosses disciplinary boundaries, multiple databases are used to ensure that key research from around the world is

not missed, and Scopus is also considered one of the most relevant databases in the field of business management (Arrigo, 2018). Web of Science was chosen as a supplementary database. Multiple databases are employed to ensure that vital research from across the world is not ignored because social media marketing research is located globally.

3.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The research purpose of this paper is to analyse research topics and future directions from SMM in CEs. Hence, the terms related to 'social media' and 'consumer electronics' were used to recognise the articles. There were no time constraints. Due to the author's language limitations, articles were only selected if they were available in both the Chinese and English languages.

To focus on sources that are likely to have the

greatest impact in the SMM discipline, the search for papers was restricted to peer-reviewed journals (Bhimani et al., 2019).

To facilitate subsequent analysis, only articles whose full text is available from the database will be used in this paper. The search strings were summarised as the expression Keyword: "social media" or "social media marketing" or "social networking", AND "consumer electronics" or "smartphone" or "laptop", then restricted document type as 'Journal article', the filter was full text.

The inclusion criteria adopted in this paper mainly include:

- One of the three databases was selected by EBSCO for duplicate articles that appear in all three databases;
- The most recent study was selected for articles reporting identical studies;
- Articles should describe the application or usage of SMM within a product, brand, or industry;
- The articles should focus on CEs;
- The articles should focus on social media.
- **The exclusion criteria adopted in this paper mainly include:**
- Full text not accessible inside the chosen database;
- The articles not composed in English or Chinese;
- The articles or reviews written in a book;
- The articles that are not related to SMM in CEs;
- The articles focus on CEs without an emphasis on SMM.
- Letters, reports, summaries, or editorial reviews (Donohue & Fox, 2000).

3.4. Search Strategy and Selection Process

There are two stages in the search strategy: the automated phase and the manually performed phase. The first automated phase is a preliminary study of the SMM of CEs products through a database search. The final keyword search found 10 articles in EBSCO Host, 24 in Scopus, and 20 in Web of Science. All of the search results articles were then subjected to the inclusion-exclusion criteria, excluding studies that were clearly not relevant to the topic, and ultimately retaining 26 articles.

The subsequent phase involves a manual search. Google's academic search engine was used to continue to find relevant studies in the selected preliminary studies (Busalim & Hussin, 2016). In Google Scholar, we also use the keywords ("social media" or "social media marketing" or "social

networking"), AND ("consumer electronics" or "smartphone" or "laptop") for searching.

These keywords were selected based on a deep understanding of the research topic and a preliminary review of previous related studies, ensuring that they can precisely hit the literature highly relevant to this research.

Considering the rapid development of the social media and consumer electronics fields, in order to obtain the latest and timely research results, the search time range is limited to the past 10 years, from 2014 to 2024. Similarly, in the search results, limit the document type to academic journal articles to ensure the quality of the literature.

At the same time, based on the number of citations, focus on the high-impact and frequently cited documents, as these often have significant academic value and wide recognition in the field. This phase was employed to guarantee the comprehensiveness and relative integrity of the systematic study (Webster & Watson, 2002), and 30 articles were eventually retained in this study.

Subsequently, applied quality evaluation is deemed essential for evaluating the quality of the preliminary study (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007). This review established four criteria for evaluating the quality of each study (Busalim & Hussin, 2016).

The following delineates these standards:

- Q1. Is this subject highly relevant to SMM in CEs?
- Q2. Is the research method specified in the paper?
- Q3. Is the data collection method described in the paper?
- Q4. Are the data analysis steps clearly described in the paper?

The process of applying quality assessment uses a three-level quality model (low, medium, and high) (Nidhra et al., 2012), with each study's quality based on its load score (Busalim & Hussin, 2016). Articles that completely fulfil the requirements will receive 2 points, studies that partially fulfil the criteria will receive 1 point, and studies that do not fulfil the criteria will receive 0 points.

A score of 5 or higher will be classified as high, a score of 4 will be classified as medium, and a score below 4 will be classified as low (Arrigo, 2018; Busalim & Hussin, 2016). After applying Q1-4, all studies were retained because they met Q1-4 standards. The results are shown in Table 1.

One study received 5 points, three received 6 points, six received 7 points, and the remaining received 8 points. 30 articles completely satisfied the quality assessment, indicating that the chosen papers might match the research objectives (Fig.2).

Table 1: Quality Assessment Result.

Study	Highly relevant	Methodology	Collection method	Data analysis description	Score	Evaluation of quality
1	2	2	2	1	7	High
2	2	2	2	2	8	High
3	2	2	2	1	7	High
4	2	2	2	2	8	High
5	1	2	2	2	7	High
6	2	2	2	2	8	High
7	2	2	2	2	8	High
8	2	2	2	2	8	High
9	2	2	2	2	8	High
10	2	2	2	2	8	High
11	2	2	2	2	8	High
12	2	2	1	2	7	High
13	1	2	1	2	6	High
14	2	2	2	2	8	High
15	2	1	2	1	6	High
16	2	2	2	2	8	High
17	2	1	1	1	5	High
18	2	2	2	2	8	High
19	2	2	2	2	8	High
20	2	2	2	2	8	High
21	2	2	2	2	8	High
22	2	2	2	2	8	High
23	2	2	2	2	8	High
24	2	2	2	1	7	High
25	2	2	2	2	8	High
26	2	2	1	1	6	High
27	2	2	2	2	8	High
28	2	2	2	2	8	High
29	2	2	2	1	7	High
30	2	2	2	2	8	High

Figure. 2: Quality Assessment Score Distribution.

3.5. Data Extraction

This procedure was implemented by carefully reviewing every study and employing a systematic research structure (Busalim & Hussin, 2016; Liang & Turban, 2011). This was accomplished by obtaining the relevant data using Zotero and Microsoft Excel spreadsheets. This study addressed the subsequent

elements for the extraction of data: Study No., author, title, publication date, research theme, outcome measures, theory, methodology, data collection method, publication source, region, and social media platform. These projects were chosen in accordance with the study aims of this article. The factors are delineated in Table 2.

Table 2: The Factors of Data Extraction.

Extracted data	Description
Study No.	The paper's number, e.g., 1, 2, 3, etc.
Author	Name of authors of the paper.
Title	The title of the paper that appears during the research phase.
Publication Date	The year the paper was published, e.g., 2020, 2021, 2022, etc.
Research Theme	The research field and main research content of the paper.
Outcome Measures	Variables or items used in the paper to measure and evaluate the final outcome.
Theory	The theory or model used in the paper, e.g., TAM, SOR, etc.
Methodology	The research methodology of the paper, e.g., quantitative, qualitative or mixed approach.
Data Collection Method	Methods of the paper data collection, e.g. survey, observation etc.
Publication Source	The journal in which the paper was published.
Region	The region or country where the study was conducted.
Social Media Platform	Social media platform for conducting research, e.g. Facebook, etc.

4. FINDINGS AND RESULTS

4.1. Findings

4.1.1. Publication Time Distribution

This study did not limit publication time during the search phase, as it has not been a long time since the concept of SMM emerged. The conception of

SMM was first proposed by the American Marketing Association in 2006, reviewed and updated in 2013 (Alves et al., 2016). As can be seen from Fig.3, the allocation of studies from 2016 to 2024. In 2022, the most publications were documented, with 11 studies. While the publication number in 2024 is not yet fully presented, it can be seen that the number of studies gradually increases after 2020 and significantly increases in 2022.

Figure 3: Publication Time Distribution.

4.1.2. Research Theme Classification

The research themes and result indicators of the 30 articles extracted in this study are listed in Table 3. Table 3 indicates that since 2016, the majority of SMM studies in the realm of CEs have been approached from the consumer perspective, with a minority focusing on the enterprise perspective. In general, it can be categorised into three distinct groups:

- 1) Study the impact of SMM on CEs brands (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2018; Cheung, Pires, & Rosenberger, 2020; Cheung, Pires, Rosenberger, et al., 2020; Malarvizhi et al., 2022; Mukherjee, 2020; Sharma & Mittal, 2019; Shuyi et al., 2022; Trivedi & Sama, 2020; Upadhyay et al., 2022);
- 2) Identify the impact of SMM on consumer's engagement, purchases or continued

purchases in CEs(Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022; Akoijam & Mazumder, 2021; Al Halbusi et al., 2022; Cheung et al., 2021; Dayal & Palsapure, 2020; Gao & Shao, 2024; Garcia-Rivera et al., 2022; Kudeshia & Kumar, 2017; Kunja et al., 2022; Majeed et al., 2023; Savitri et al., 2022; Trivedi & Sama, 2020; Wahid et al., 2023; Wang

& Khan, 2022);

3) Examine the effectiveness of SMM in CEs industry(Čeněk et al., 2016; Chakraborty & Bhat, 2019; Gupta & Singh, 2017; Huifen & Yuanwei, 2016; Mirzaei et al., 2022; Pezoa-Fuentes et al., 2023; Pre et al., 2022; Vollero et al., 2021).

Table 3: Research Themes and Outcome Measures.

Study	Research Theme	Outcome Measures
1	to examine the determinants influencing an individual's intention to continue purchasing online on Amazon.in	service quality, relative price, advantage, trust
2	to ascertain whether opinion leaders and opinion seekers are separate constructions in the online environment	online opinion leader and online opinion seeker
3	to examine the relative impact of fundamental factors on consumer purchasing satisfaction, and the effect of customer satisfaction with online transactions on the desire to continue using the website	customer satisfaction with online purchases
4	to ascertain primary catalysts for the Amazon effect based on consumer feedback on social media	consumer expectations
5	to explore the sustainable supply chain trade-offs	SSC practices, the perception of customers
6	to address literature deficiencies regarding the application of adaptive marketing on social media platforms through the observation of consumer and sales force behavior	customer satisfaction, repurchase intention, and customer loyalty
7	to investigate the impact of user-generated positive electronic word-of-mouth on Facebook on brand attitude and its subsequent effect on purchase intention	social eWOM, brand attitude, purchase intention
8	to identify and examine the factors affecting consumer loyalty through SMM	customer commitment
9	to analyse the components of SMMAs and their impact on brand equity concerning brand awareness, brand image, brand loyalty, and readiness to pay a premium price	brand awareness, brand image, brand loyalty and willingness to pay premium price
10	to examine the correlation of SMM, Brand Image and Purchase Intention	purchase Intention
11	to examine the impact of online reviews on functional and hedonic brand perceptions	brand image
12	to elucidate the influence of eWOM on the purchasing intentions of young customers	buying intentions
13	to analyse the impact of several factors on online purchasing intention	online purchase intention
14	to assess the impact of various activities on Twitter on engagement	engagement
15	to evaluate the level of the Facebook communication of selected Czech e-shops	posts and reactions
16	to ascertain the prevailing sentiment and emotions on Twitter via sentiment analysis	the predominant sentiment and prevailing emotions
17	to evaluate the function of YouTube as a contemporary customer-centric strategy employed by firms for guerilla marketing	advertisements
18	to analyse the impact of content attributes, linguistic elements, and nonverbal cues on social media interaction	social media engagement
19	to investigate the impact of brand interactivity within social media regarding consumer-brand engagement and its associated results	consumer-brand engagement
20	to analyse the impact of social media on buyer reactions through the development of brand equity and brand trust	consumer response(WTPPP)

21	to examine the influence of SMM initiatives on consumer purchase intentions using customer equity determinants	purchase Intentions
22	to analyse the function of SMM in fostering value co-creation and customer brand engagement, together with repurchase intention and continuous search activity as behavioral reactions	value co-creation and consumer-brand engagement (CBE)
23	to investigate the key components of SMMAAs and assess their impact on brand equity, relationship equity, and purchase intention	brand equity (BE), relationship equity (RE) and purchase intention (PI)
24	to examine the efficacy of SMM in stimulating arousal or enthusiasm for the promoted companies and ultimately fostering purchase intention	Purchase intention, Brand passion
25	to investigate the influence of SMM components on consumer-brand interaction and brand knowledge	consumer-brand engagement and brand knowledge
26	to study the SMM activities effect	brand equity, customer response
27	to study how major consumer electronics brands carry out content marketing on wechat public accounts	content marketing
28	to study the impact of influencer endorsements on brand attitude, subsequently fostering brand appreciation, ultimately influencing online purchase intentions	attitude toward the brand and purchase intentions
29	to furnish comprehensive insights into how various social media platforms and tools have markedly influenced the success of online retail enterprises	business performance
30	to Investigate how consumer-brand engagement in the smartphone industry drives brand love and WOM under the influence of brand interaction and consumer engagement	eWOM

4.1.3. Theoretical Foundations

Among the 30 empirical articles extracted, 25 have a clear theoretical basis, and the remaining 5 have no clear theoretical foundations. It is worth mentioning that 5 articles use more than one theory. Fig.4 lists the theoretical underpinnings that researchers use when studying SMM in CEs. We

observed that 20 distinct theories were identified within the body of knowledge of the articles included, and most of them focused on behavioral theory. Among them, the number of papers using Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is the highest, with 5 papers. The next four articles all used the Stimuli-Organism-Response Model (SOR). Two articles each apply Uses and Gratifications Theory (UGT) and Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA).

Figure 4: Distributions of Theoretical Foundations.

4.1.4. Research Methodologies

As can be seen from Fig. 5, researches on SMM in CE's products were mainly quantitative researches,

with 25 articles choosing this methodology, accounting for 84% of all selected articles. The mixed approach methods were applied in 4 papers, and only 1 study used qualitative research methodology.

Figure 5: Distribution of Research Methodologies.

Figure 6 shows the data collection methods for 30 articles, 67% of which used survey methods, such as questionnaires or online surveys (Al Halbusi et al., 2022; Dayal & Palsapure, 2020; Gao & Shao, 2024; Kudeshia & Kumar, 2017; Majeed et al., 2023; Malarvizhi et al., 2022; Savitri et al., 2022). 30% of the articles used observation methods, such as observation of tweets posted on Twitter, observation of likes and comments on Tiktok, or marketing content text of brand public accounts on Wechat, etc (Garcia-Rivera et al., 2022; Huifen & Yuanwei, 2016; Pezoa-Fuentes et al., 2023; Wahid et al., 2023). 3% of the articles used case study method to investigate the case of Chinese CE's brand Huawei in Thailand (Wang & Khan, 2022).

4.1.5. Region Distribution

As can be seen from the regional distribution of the research (Fig. 7), SMM research in the field of CE's is mainly concentrated in developing countries, especially in China and India, which are the major producers and consumers of CE's. In addition to works that present observations from a worldwide sample framework (1 article) and the not specifying the region (1 article), the Indian region has the most research, a total of 13 articles. This is followed by 5 studies on the Chinese market. Further research reveals that there are also more studies on Southeast Asia region, for example, there are 2 papers on Indonesia, and 1 paper each on Thailand, Malaysia and the Philippines.

Figure 6: Percentage of Data Collection Method.

Figure 7: Distribution of Region.

5. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 The Primary Research Questions and the Current Condition of the Art

5.1.1. Influence of SMM on CEs Brands

SMM was discovered to be able to play significant positive influence on CEs brands. All the components of SMM activities have significant effects on the improvement of brand equity, especially on brand awareness and brand image. Among them, entertainment, trendiness, customisation and e-WOM are the primary drivers for enhancing brand awareness and brand image (Malarvizhi *et al.*, 2022). SMM can let customers understand the products, quality, brand value and service offered by the CEs companies, moreover, it also can influence customer trust, confidence and engagement. The quality of service, loyalty to the brand, awareness of the brand, and the association with the brand and other factors will affect the company's brand equity (Sharma & Mittal, 2019). The influence of consumer brand engagement on brand awareness and brand image is substantial and noteworthy, with the majority of SMM aspects exerting considerable indirect effects on brand knowledge (Cheung, Pires, & Rosenberger, 2020). Although the overall impact of SMM on CEs brands is consistent, some studies focus on SMM activities as a whole, while some studies focus on a particular form of SMM or a particular manifestation of SMM. For instance, credible online comments in social media have substantial beneficial impacts on brand image, and have a greater impact on hedonic brand image (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2018). Brand interactivity on social media, including entertainment interactivity, cognitive information-transfer interaction, and cognitive latest data interactivity, serves to improve consumer-brand engagement, which strongly and consistently influences cooperation and intent to repurchase (Cheung, Pires, Rosenberger, *et al.*, 2020). For the marketing communication of CEs products, although both specialised influencers and attractive celebrity effects have significant effects on brand attitudes, the selection of influential experts is more advantageous than attractive celebrities, and brand attitudes greatly impact brand admiration, which eventually results in intentions to buy online (Trivedi & Sama, 2020). In addition, users-generated positive electronic WOM on the social media platforms like Facebook can also significantly impact consumer attitudes toward CEs brands (Kudeshia & Kumar, 2017).

Accordingly, it can be concluded that whether it is

to enhance brand image, brand equity or brand loyalty, CEs brands should use SMM to strengthen their customer relationships.

5.1.2. Influence of SMM on Consumers' Behaviour

SMM of CEs can have a beneficial effect on consumers' behavior such as consumer engagement, purchase intention, or continued purchase intention. It not only informs consumers about the products, quality and services offered by the companies, but also affects consumer trust, confidence and response (Sharma & Mittal, 2019). In general, informational content, represented by comments, positively impacts customer social media engagement for highly engaged brands, and informational content elicits greater social media engagement than emotional content (Wahid *et al.*, 2023). SMM components are indicators of consumer value co-creation orientation and engagement that positively influence consumer behavior (e.g., persistent search behavior, etc.). Brand interactivity in social media also has a significant impact on consumer brand engagement. For example, (perceived) brand interaction plays a key role in establishing the connection between buyers and mobile device brands on Sina Weibo in China. This reciprocal advantageous engagement makes it more likely that Chinese consumers will find smartphone brands attractive and valuable, and then react intellectually and emotionally, and positively to these extensively engaging brands (Gao & Shao, 2024). Social media platforms serve as a crucial instrument for enterprises in the CEs sector. Within the social network, companies use the marketing media, not only to announce new goods through authenticated accounts, but also as a prompt and accessible customer service solution (Garcia-Rivera *et al.*, 2022). Entertainment, trendiness, personalisation, informativeness, interaction, and word of mouth are all parts of SMM activities that make customers more likely to buy. This is because they give customers more value by giving them up-to-date, trendy, and real information about new products, discounts, and offers; creative ads that are fun to look at; more interaction by giving customers ways to talk directly with the brand; and e-word of mouth, which is also encouraged by letting customers read and write reviews and testimonials about each other on social media sites (Aggarwal & Mittal, 2022). In the mobile device environment, electronic word-of-mouth has a substantial impact on purchase intention. Especially for young people, both hedonic and utilitarian attitudes influence their purchase intentions (Kunja

et al., 2022). The utilisation of social media in sales in the CE retail market exerts a beneficial influence on adaptive selling practices, and social media and adaptive selling techniques used by Salesforce can contribute to build repeat purchase intention and client contentment (Majeed et al., 2023). Through the use of SMM, products can achieve more recognition among consumers distant from their manufacturer's location, which improves consumer purchasing decisions (Savitri et al., 2022).

5.1.3. The Effectiveness of SMM in CEs Industry

The use of SMM in the CEs industry can be effective in improving business performance. During the age of mobile Internet, the specificity of consumer electronic products is manifested in the large number of highly viscous users. Sharing and spreading information about a brand on social media helps people learn more about it, believe it, and be more aware of it. This gives the brand the premium of social currency (Huifen & Yuanwei, 2016). Some of the dimensions like Reach and Share-ability show how popular YouTube is as a social media tool. These all help to make YouTube an important tool for marketing communications (Gupta & Singh, 2017). The perceived ease of use of social media tools directly affects social media advertising, which in turn positively affects business performance. In addition, social media advertising also positively affects e-WOM, if online merchants have better e-WOM, then they may interact, communicate, and establish profitable relationships with their clients, resulting in improved business success (Pre et al., 2022). A sentiment analysis of the CEs industry on Twitter reveals that positive reviews dominate and emotions such as anticipation and confidence are the most representative, so companies can use tools such as Twitter to make judicious choices to strengthen their consumer engagement and retention strategies (Pezoa-Fuentes et al., 2023). Hence, merchants can increase the frequency of contact with their followers by posting more frequently on social media platforms and focusing on posting engaging and shareable viral content to improve management and marketing (Čeněk et al., 2016).

5.1.4. Contradictions and Integration in Research

Interestingly, when we analysed these documents, we also discovered some contradictory points. Firstly, unlike most studies that emphasise the core role of trust, in the purchase of consumer electronics in India, trust does not directly affect the purchase intention (Dayal & Palsapure, 2020). This

might be because consumers view trust as the basis for decision-making rather than a differentiating factor; while in emerging markets (such as Ghana), trust remains the core driving force, and trust takes effect indirectly through the adaptive behavior of salespeople (Majeed et al., 2023). Secondly, the failure of some dimensions of SMMA highlights regional demand differences. For example, entertainment value was ineffective in the research on China during the pandemic (Shuyi et al., 2022), and interactivity failed in the portable device scenario in Malaysia (Malarvizhi et al., 2022), indicating that consumers attach different weights to the functionality and entertainment value of information in different situations. We also found that consumers in emerging markets (such as India and Ghana) place more emphasis on price/brand equity (Akoijam & Mazumder, 2021), while consumers in mature markets (such as Italy) are influenced by the "Amazon effect", and pay more attention to price or after-sales service (Vollero et al., 2021). This indicates that marketing strategies in different geographical regions need to be differentiated. In emerging markets, it is necessary to emphasise the display of cost-effectiveness, while in mature markets, it is necessary to improve service standards. Additionally, e-commerce platforms (such as Amazon.in) mainly rely on logistics or price advantages to drive repeat purchases (Dayal & Palsapure, 2020), and social media (such as Facebook/TikTok) relies on opinion leaders and UGC (Wahid et al., 2023). Brands or enterprises need to consider transactional demand-oriented e-commerce platforms and information search-oriented social media. It should also be noted that opinion seekers are driven by the quality of comments and the credibility of the source, and are more sensitive to hedonic brand images (Chakraborty & Bhat, 2018), while experts in opinion leaders are more effective than celebrities (Trivedi & Sama, 2020).

5.2. The Implications and Limitations in Current Research

5.2.1. Theoretical Implication

This paper finds that the subject of SMM for CEs is a comparatively new addition to the scholarly literature. The initial study on this specific topic was published in 2016, and to this day, research in this domain remains limited, focusing on disparate concerns. As can be seen from the examination of the research methodologies used in the study (Fig. 5), there are no literature review articles on SMM in the field of CEs. Consequently, this systematic literature

review provided in this paper helps to fill this obvious lacuna in research. First, this study extends the limited research on SMM of CEs and its impact. For the first time, current research is systematically summarised and analysed from a review perspective, providing clear guidance on SMM in the CEs industry. According to all included studies, SMM can provide unique value to CEs brands, companies, and consumers, successfully influencing consumer behavior and increasing business performance. Second, social media has been regarded as an effective channel for marketing communication of CEs products, and the study areas are mainly focused on India, China, and Southeast Asian countries. However, as one of the major countries in the production and distribution of CEs, China's social media platforms are different from other regions, and there is no research focusing on the effectiveness of China's social media platforms (WeChat, Xiaohongshu, Weibo, etc.) on CEs marketing. In fact, WeChat, Douyin, Kuaishou, QQ, Xiaohongshu, etc. are typical social platforms frequently used by Chinese netizens. Among them, the usage rate of WeChat is as high as 94.3 % (CNNIC, 2025). Compared with other Western countries, Chinese social media platforms have characteristics such as fragmented platforms and complex marketing. Enterprises or brand owners need to invest a large amount of resources and expertise, including establishing networks with local partners, to cope with the complex social media environment (Chiu *et al.*, 2012). Therefore, a research question exists here: What is the effectiveness of marketing disseminated on various social media platforms in China? Is it consistent with what is disseminated on foreign social media platforms? Third, regarding the use of social media to attract and retain customers, more research could be conducted to understand how social media platforms change consumer behavior in CEs. For example, how can brand image and brand trust be further enhanced? How can managers promote consumer perceptions of brands? How consumers' will perceived value, brand trust and brand image affect consumer behavior? These questions all contribute to a deeper understanding of their impact on customer engagement and loyalty. Fourth, with the rapid renewal of CEs products, and fierce competition among brands, both local and foreign brands will utilise social media to promote their products. Indeed, local brands utilise advantages such as cultural background to maintain their position in the minds of consumers; however, foreign brands also improve their marketing strategies to attract

consumers. In this context, how effective is the SMM of local and foreign brands? Will consumers change their consumption behavior because of the brand's geography? All these questions deserve further research in the future.

5.2.2. Implications for Practice

CEs managers need the same broad market expertise to connect with their customers, and social media provides them with an effective marketing instrument to accomplish this goal. This study provides brand managers of CEs with perceptions into how to develop a SMM strategy to unlock brand capability and improve business performance. The three research themes summarised all have managerial implications that support managers of CEs to take a more active role in enhancing their products through digital and social media technologies. The findings highlight the importance for CEs brands to create social media platforms that both fulfill customer needs and foster customer affection for their brands and products. First and foremost, they should be able to utilise SMM campaigns to enhance brand equity, thereby effectively communicating the value of CEs brands. Second, managers can determine the substance of marketing communications on digital platforms by focusing on entertainment, interaction, trends, customisation, and word-of-mouth to increase consumer engagement and inspire purchasing behavior. Finally, if consumer electronics managers want to optimise their brand's performance on social media, they must pay attention to the ongoing development of SMM and attract customers' attention through effective tweets and advertisements.

5.2.3. The Limitations of the Research

The focus of this study is to examine all previous studies related to SMM within the CEs sector (Table 4). Nevertheless, there are also some limitations to this study. First, the research literature included in this paper is not sufficient. Because of the limited selection of databases, there is still a lot of relevant and high-quality literature that has not been included in the current study, which may contain research on other topics of SMM. Future research could consider these studies conducted in different contexts. Second, while this study contributed by searching, categorising, and summarising the primary studies, it may be more advantageous to collect quantitative data by conducting meta-analytical studies, especially since several quantitative studies have been conducted in the area of the impact of SMM on

consumers and brands.

Table 4: Theoretical and Practice Implications Framework based on the Research.

Research themes	Current research	Theoretical implication	Managerial implication
Influence of SMM on CE brands	SMM was found to be able to play significant positive influence on CE brands. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> All the elements of SMM activities have significant effects on the improvement of brand equity. A particular form or manifestation of SMM has significant positive effects on CE brands. 	How can brand image and brand trust be further enhanced? How effective is the social media marketing of local and foreign brands?	Managers should be able to utilise SMM campaigns to enhance brand equity, thereby effectively communicating the value of CE brands.
Influence of SMM on consumers' behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> SMM of CE products can have a positive impact on consumers' behavior. SMM elements are indicators of consumer value co-creation orientation and engagement that positively influence consumer behavior. The six elements of SMM activities all positively affect customers' purchase intentions. 	How can managers promote consumer perceptions of brands? How consumers' will perceived value, brand trust and brand image affect consumer behavior? Will consumers change their consumption behavior because of the brand's geography?	Managers can determine the content of marketing communications on social media by focusing on entertainment, interaction, trends, customisation, and word-of-mouth to increase consumer engagement and inspire purchasing behavior.
The effectiveness of SMM in CEs industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of SMM in the CE industry can be effective in improving business performance. help make it a hub for marketing communications. Merchants can increase the frequency of contact with their followers to improve management and marketing. 	What is the effectiveness of marketing disseminated on various social media platforms in China? Is it consistent with what is disseminated on foreign social media platforms?	Managers must pay attention to the ongoing development of SMM and attract customers' attention through effective tweets and advertisements.

6. CONCLUSION

This paper provides an overview of the development of the scholarly literature on SMM for consumer electronics up to this point and categorises the key research themes that have emerged to provide a clear overview of SMM research for CEs. The academic relevance of this research is related to the growing importance of social media in the CEs industry with the aim of improving marketing management in the CEs industry, enhancing customer relationships and identifying new business opportunities.

With the widespread adoption of AIGC technology, brands can generate localised content on a large scale. However, it remains unknown whether the AI-generated content can truly understand and touch upon consumers from different cultural backgrounds. Therefore, the future research direction must fully utilise AI and big data technologies. To help future scholars and managers allocate research resources more effectively, we draw on the Eisenhower Matrix and classify the possible future research directions based on the two dimensions of "importance" and "urgency" to clarify their priority (Table 5).

Table 5: Research Priority Matrix.

	Urgent	Not Urgent
Important	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Research on the Generation of Cross-Cultural Marketing Content and the Effectiveness of Emotional Resonance Driven by AI. Research on the Dynamic Evolution of Trust Advantage of Domestic Brands in China and the Response Strategies of Foreign Brands. The specific paths through which real live-streamers and virtual live-streamers affect consumers' purchasing decisions, trust, and satisfaction. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Explore how a brand can transform from a mere product seller to a community organiser with shared values through social media. A Study on the Long-Term Impact of Algorithm Evolution on Brand-Consumer Relationships on Social Media Platforms.
Not Important	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In specific hot events, analyse how sudden social hotspots affect brand reputation and communication strategies. Comparative analysis of the effectiveness of different types of KOLs (such as celebrities vs. experts vs. KOC) in social media marketing. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Verification of the applicability of traditional marketing models on a single social platform. The short-term impact of minor changes on different social platforms on user engagement.

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